

Kinetics of the Hydrolytic Decomposition of Acetamide with Peroxodisulphate

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Kinetics of the Ag(I) ion-catalysed decomposition of acetamide has been investigated. The total order of the reaction is unity, being first order with respect to peroxodisulphate and zero order with respect to acetamide. The activation energy and the entropy of activation for the silver-ion catalysed process have been found to 13,483 cal. mole⁻¹ and -28.78 e. u. respectively. A suitable mechanism, involving the formation of higher-valent silver intermediates, has been formulated. The hydrolytic decomposition of acetamide by peroxodisulphate in presence of silver ions yields acetic acid.

Kinetics of the oxidation of organic nitrogen compounds by peroxodisulphate has received very little attention so far. Decomposition of a few other organic and inorganic compounds by this oxidant¹ has, however, been reported. Silver ions are usually found to catalyse all such decomposition processes and recently colloidal silver has also been used as a catalyst for such oxidations². In the present communication, kinetics of the Ag(I) ion-catalysed decomposition of acetamide has been studied with peroxodisulphate ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

An aqueous solution of potassium peroxodisulphate (A.R., B.D.H.) was always prepared fresh by dissolving the exact weight so as to avoid its slight change in concentration on keeping for a few days. All other chemicals used were also A.R., B.D.H. or of extra pure quality and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. An aqueous solution of acetamide was estimated by the saponification method due to Olsen³.

The solutions of acetamide and silver nitrate of suitable concentrations were taken in 150-ml Pyrex conical flasks and were placed in a bath maintained at the desired temperature within the range of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The potassium peroxodisulphate solution was placed separately in the same bath. After some time, both solutions were rapidly mixed. Aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at definite intervals of time and the amount of un-consumed peroxodisulphate was determined iodometrically by the method of Szabo *et al.*⁴

The calculated first-order rate constants were found to be fairly satisfactory and the results obtained were quite reproducible. One set of experimental data is presented in Table I.

1. House, *Chem. Rev.*, 1962, 62, 185.
2. Virendra Singh, Doctoral thesis, Allahabad University, 1964.
3. *Dis Chemistry*, 1943, 56, 202.
4. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1962, 135, 269.

TABLE I

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.02M$, $CH_3CONH_2 = 0.1M$, $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$, Temp. = $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Time.	Hypo.	$(k/2.303) \times 10^4$ (min^{-1}).	Time.	Hypo.	$(k/2.303) \times 10^4$ (min^{-1}).
0 min.	5.00 ml	..	180 min.	3.78 ml	6.74
30	4.76	7.01	210	3.60	6.76
60	4.54	6.98	240	3.46	6.66
90	4.36	6.83	270	3.30	6.69
120	4.14	6.83	300	3.14	6.72
150	3.98	6.60			Av. 6.73
					or $k = 15.50 \times 10^{-4} \text{min}^{-1}$.

Effect of Peroxodisulphate Concentrations.—To determine the order of the reaction with respect to peroxodisulphate, three different concentrations of the oxidant were employed. First-order rate constants obtained were found to be fairly agreeing. The results of the effect of various concentrations of peroxodisulphate on the reaction rate are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Conditions same as in Table I.

Initial conc. of the oxidant (M)	..	0.01	0.02	0.04
$k \times 10^4$ (min^{-1})	..	17.35	15.50	13.25

The reaction rate appears from Table II to decrease with increasing concentrations of peroxodisulphate. This decrease is attributed to the inhibiting action of K^+ ions, which are known to inhibit peroxodisulphate oxidations of other organic nitrogen compounds, reported earlier⁵ from these laboratories, and which has further been confirmed by adding potassium nitrate to the reaction mixture when the constants are diminished.

Effect of Acetamide Concentrations.—To determine the total order of the reaction, the effect of different concentrations of acetamide (much higher than that of peroxodisulphate) on the reaction rate was studied. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Conditions same as in Table I.

Initial conc. of CH_3CONH_2 (M)	..	0.8	0.4	0.2	0.1
$k \times 10^4$ (min^{-1})	..	20.86	19.20	17.29	15.50

The rate constants (Table III) show a tendency to increase with increasing concentrations of acetamide. The order of this reaction with respect to acetamide, on calculating by isolation method, comes out to be 0.11. It is therefore concluded that the order of the reaction with respect to acetamide, which is slightly positive but fractional, is zero.

5. Agrawal and Mushran, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 629.

Effect of Silver Nitrate Concentrations.—The effect of four different concentrations of silver ions on the reaction rate was studied. In Table IV are presented the average values of rate constants for various concentrations of AgNO_3 .

TABLE IV
Conditions same as in Table I.

Initial conc. of AgNO_3 .	First-order rate constants.	k for unit conc.
0.0006M	$6.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.88
0.0010	16.50	1.55
0.0020	27.58	1.39
0.0040	52.16	1.30

Fig. 1 represents the plots of the rate constants versus concentrations of silver nitrate and shows that the rate constants increase with increasing concentrations of silver nitrate in a linear manner. Further, these plots do not exactly pass through the origin, suggesting slight possibility of the uncatalysed decomposition of acetamide. Investigations, however, show that the uncatalysed decomposition does not proceed with practically measurable velocity.

FIG. 1
 $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.02 \text{ M}$. $\text{CH}_3\text{CONH}_2 = 0.10 \text{ M}$.

Effect of Temperature.—The effect of temperature on the rate constants of the decomposition of acetamide with peroxodisulphate is shown in Table V.

TABLE V	
Temp.	.. 30° 35° 40° 45°
$k \times 10^4 (\text{min}^{-1})$	.. 10.04 15.50 22.36 32.01

Energy of Activation.—The energy of activation was calculated graphically from the slope of the plots of $\log k$ versus $1/T$. The results are recorded in Table VI.

TABLE VI				
Initial conc. of $\text{AgNO}_3 (M)$	..	0.001	0.002	0.004
Energy of activation (cal. mole ⁻¹)	..	13,770	13,170	13,500

The variation in the concentration of silver nitrate employed evidently has no appreciable effect on the energy of activation and its average value comes out to be 13,480 cal. From this average value of energy of activation, the frequency factor and entropy of

activation have been calculated as -49.81×10^5 litres mole⁻¹ min⁻¹ and -28.8 s.u. respectively.

DISCUSSION

For the interpretation of the kinetic data, the mechanism of the oxidation process is postulated to involve production of the radical $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$, which acts as initiator.

For the silver-ion catalysed decomposition of acetamide by peroxodisulphate, the univalent silver ion is oxidised to higher bivalent or trivalent state by interaction with sulphate radical ($\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$) and these higher-valent states of silver act as oxidising agents for the reducing substrate. Thus:

An alternative step⁶ has also been suggested to explain the catalytic effect of silver ions:

followed by either

or

The formation of bivalent silver has also been suggested by the relation:

The nature of these higher-valent silver intermediates, thus formed, has not yet been fully established. The formation of trivalent silver has been proposed by Yost⁷; Malaguti⁸ has suggested the silver intermediates to be bivalent. Formation of these higher-valent states of silver has also been proposed by Mushran *et al.*⁹ for explaining the mechanisms of the various oxidation reactions, catalysed by colloidal silver. The results of the investigation of the decomposition of acetamide by persulphate show that the velocity of oxidation is proportional to the concentrations of silver ions and peroxodisulphate. Thus for the silver-ion catalysed oxidation, the loss of peroxodisulphate may be represented as

$$-d/dt (\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}) = k(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}) (\text{Ag}^{1+})$$

The above equation indicates that the reaction is of zero order with respect to acetamide. Our experimental data also show that the concentration of acetamide has little

6. Bekier and Kijowski, *Chem. Abs.*, 1936, 30, 3306; Chaltykyan and Beilerian, *ibid.*, 1958, 52, 18054.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 152.

8. *Anal. Chim. Rome*, 1955, 41, 241.

9. Singh and Mushran, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 551.

effect on the reaction rate. The mechanism of the silver-ion catalysed decomposition of acetamide therefore is as

The above step consisting of two-electron transfer is a slow step and controls the rate of decomposition. This step is followed by the fast step leading to hydrolytic decomposition of substrate(S) as follows:

Here the decomposition is effected by the abstraction of two hydrogen ions by solvent water and the oxygen being made available to substrate (S), the trivalent silver being itself converted to a lower-valent state.

The end product of the hydrolytic decomposition of acetamide by peroxodisulphate in presence of silver ions is acetic acid, represented by the stoichiometric equation:

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